

On the Dihedral Cohomology of Graded Banach Algebras

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Abstract.

We are concerned with the dihedral cohomology of a unital $\mathbb{Z}/2$ -graded Banach algebra A over $K = \mathbb{C}$ with a graded involution and study some properties of it. It is considered the prototype example of graded algebras with topology.

Keywords: Graded Banach algebras - dihedral cohomology.

1 $\mathbb{Z}/2$ -graded Banach algebras with graded involutions.

In this section we introduce some basic concepts and facts concerning $\mathbb{Z}/2$ -graded Banach algebras.

Definition (1.1) [11]:

A norm on a vector space V is a map $\|\cdot\|:V \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, such that :

- 1- $\|x\| \geq 0$ for all $x \in V$, and $\|x\| = 0 \Leftrightarrow x = 0$;
- 2- $\|\alpha x\| = |\alpha| \|x\|$ for all $x \in V$ and $\alpha \in \mathbb{C}$;
- 3- $\|x + y\| \leq \|x\| + \|y\|$ for all $x, y \in V$.

Then $(V, \|\cdot\|)$ is a normed space. A norm on V induces a metric d on V by $d(x, y) = \|x - y\|$. We say that $(V, \|\cdot\|)$ is complete if the metric space (V, d) is (Cauchy) complete. Complete normed vector spaces are called Banach spaces. For a normed space V and $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}$, we write

$$V_{[\lambda]} = \{x \in V : \|x\| \leq \lambda\}.$$

Thus $V_{[1]}$ is the closed unit ball of V .

The maps between Banach spaces are the maps which preserve both the linear structure and the topology. Such maps are bounded linear maps, or operators.

Lemma (1.2) [9]:

Let $T :V \rightarrow W$ be a linear map between Banach spaces, then :

- 1- T is continuous with respect to the norms on V and W ;
- 2- T is continuous at 0 ;
- 3- For some $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}$, we have $\|T(X)\| \leq \lambda \|x\|$ for all $x \in V$. T is bounded such that :

$$\lambda_{\min} = \|T\| = \sup \{ \|T(x)\| / \|x\| : x \in V, x \neq 0 \}.$$

Definition (1.3) [3]:

A Banach algebra is an algebra A with a norm $\|\cdot\|$ such that $(A, \|\cdot\|)$ is a Banach space with the property,

$$\|ab\| \leq \|a\| \|b\| \text{ for all } a, b \in A .$$

Definition (1.4) [2]:

A Banach algebra A is called a simplicially trivial if $H^n(A, A^* \ni \{ \})$, for all $n = 0, 1, \dots$, where $A^* = Hom_K(A, K)$ is the topological dual space of A . C^* -algebras can be thought of as special Banach algebras [1].

Definition (1.5) [1]:

Let A be an algebra. A map $*$: $A \rightarrow A$, $a \mapsto a^*$, is an involution if :

- 1- $(\lambda a + b)^* = \bar{\lambda} a^* + b^*$ for all $\lambda \in \mathbb{C}$ and $a, b \in A$;
- 2- $(ab)^* = b^* a^*$ for all $a, b \in A$;
- 3- $(a^*)^* = a$ for all $a \in A$.

Remark :

A map $*$: $A \rightarrow A$; $a \mapsto a^*$, is an involution if $*^2 = id_A : A \rightarrow A$. For all

$a, b \in A$, we have $*(a) = b$ and $*(b) = a$, then $*^2(a) = (*(a)) = *(b) = a$, i.e.

$$*^2 = id_A .$$

Definition (1.6) [1]:

Let A be a Banach algebra. The pair $(A, *)$ is called a C^* -algebra if

$$\|a^* a\| = \|a\|^2 \text{ for all } a \in A .$$

Definition (1.7):

Let G be a finite group with unit e , and A be a unital complex Banach algebra. A G -graded structure for A is a decomposition $A = \bigoplus_{g \in G} A_g$, where $A_g \subseteq A$ and $A_g A_h \subseteq A_{g+h}$ for all $g, h \in G$, $\bigoplus$ is the direct sum.

An element $a \in A_g$ is a homogenous element of degree $|a| = g$, it is called nontrivial homogenous if $g \neq e$.

Example (1.8):

For the group $G = \mathbb{Z}_2 = \{0, 1\}$ and $A = A_0 \oplus A_1$, we have $A_g A_h \subseteq A_{g+h} \pmod{2}$, for all $g, h \in G$, and

$$|a| = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } a \in A_0 \text{ (} a \text{ even)} \\ 1 & \text{if } a \in A_1 \text{ (} a \text{ odd)} \end{cases} .$$

For the reflexive group $G = \mathbb{Z}/2 = \{-1, +1\}$ of order 2 and $A = A^+ \oplus A^-$,

we have $A_g A_h \subseteq A_{g+h}$, for all $g, h \in G$.

Remark :

A morphism $f : A \rightarrow A$ is a graded if $f(A_g) \subseteq A_g$, for all $g \in G$. Firstly, we recall some definitions and facts we need here. See [8]. We set up the theory of $\mathbb{Z}/2$ -graded Banach spaces, complexes and algebras. Let K ($K = \mathbb{C}$) be a field such that $ch(K) = 0$, and $\alpha \in \{+, -\}$ which we identify with $\{+1, -1\}$. A Banach space V is a complete normed vector space $(V, \|\cdot\|)$.

Definition (1.9) [8] :

A $\mathbb{Z}/2$ -graded Banach space is a K -Banach space V equipped with an involution $\#: V \rightarrow V$, defined by $x \rightarrow \alpha x$, ($x \in V$, $\alpha = \pm$). It is also, a $K[\mathbb{Z}/2]$ -module V .

Lemma (1.10) [8]:

A $\mathbb{Z}/2$ -graded K -Banach space V is trivially graded if :

- (a) V is a trivial $K[\mathbb{Z}/2]$ -module; or
- (b) $V = V^+$ or $\# = id_V$.

Proof :

If $V = V^+$, then $x \in V^+$, $|x| = 0$ and $\alpha = +$, hence $\#(x) = \alpha x = x$, i.e. $\# = id_V$.

If $\# = id_V$, then $\#(x) = x$, hence $\#^2(x) = \#(\#(x)) = \#(x) = x$, i.e. $\alpha = +$ or $V = V^+$

Remark:

A map of $\mathbb{Z}/2$ -graded Banach spaces is a bounded linear map (continuous) $f : V \rightarrow W$, i.e. $V^\alpha \mapsto W^\alpha$, $\alpha = \pm$, or commutes with $\#$ or a map of $K[\mathbb{Z}/2]$ -modules.

Definition (1.11)[8]:

A positively graded complex of Banach spaces

$$V_* = \{ \dots \rightarrow V_2 \xrightarrow{d} V_1 \xrightarrow{d} V_0 \rightarrow 0 \}$$

is a $\mathbb{Z}/2$ -graded complex if all Banach spaces V_i ($i \geq 0$) are $\mathbb{Z}/2$ -graded and all differentials $d : V_i \rightarrow V_{i-1}$ are maps of $\mathbb{Z}/2$ -graded spaces.

Now, we can define the $\mathbb{Z}/2$ -graded Banach algebra.

Definition (1.12) [8]:

A $\mathbb{Z}/2$ -graded Banach algebra is an associative unital K -Banach algebra A such that the multiplication is a map $\pi : A \otimes A \rightarrow A$ of

$\mathbb{Z}/2$ -graded Banach spaces. That is:

- (a) the involution $\#: A \rightarrow A$ is a homomorphism of Banach algebras : $\#(ab) = \#(a)\#(b)$ for all $a, b \in A$, or

(b) $A^\alpha A^\beta \subset A^{\alpha\beta}, (\alpha, \beta \in \{\pm 1\})$.

Remark:

The multiplication $\pi : A \otimes A \rightarrow A$ is a bounded linear map (continuous) as $\|\pi(a \otimes b)\| \mapsto \|ab\| \leq \|a\| \|b\|$ for all $a, b \in A$.

Example (1.13) [8]:

Any $\mathbb{Z}$ -graded Banach algebra $A = \bigoplus_{n \in \mathbb{Z}} A_n$ gives rise to a $\mathbb{Z}/2$ -graded Banach algebra B defined by $B = B^+ + B^-$, where, $B^+ = \bigoplus_n A_{2n}$ and $B^- = \bigoplus_n A_{2n+1}$.

Remark:

The involution given on $C_n(A) = A^{\otimes(n+1)}, n = 0, 1, \dots$, by the grading over $\mathbb{Z}/2$ is given by: $\#: C_n(A) \rightarrow C_n(A)$, such that $\#(a_0 \otimes \dots \otimes a_n) = \#(a_0) \otimes \dots \otimes \#(a_n)$, for all $a_0, \dots, a_n \in A$. It commutes with the differential $b_n : C_n(A) \rightarrow C_{n-1}(A)$, defined by

$$b_n(a_0 \otimes \dots \otimes a_n) = \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} (-1)^i a_0 \otimes \dots \otimes a_i a_{i+1} \otimes \dots \otimes a_n + (-1)^{n+|a_n|(|a_0|+\dots+|a_{n-1}|)} a_n a_0 \otimes a_1 \otimes \dots \otimes a_{n-1},$$

and cyclic operator $t_n : C_n(A) \rightarrow C_n(A)$, defined by

$$t_n(a_0 \otimes \dots \otimes a_{n-1} \otimes a_n) = (-1)^{|a_n|(|a_0|+\dots+|a_{n-1}|)} a_n \otimes a_0 \otimes \dots \otimes a_{n-1}.$$

In other words, $\#b = b\#$ and $\#t = t\#$.

Now, we can define the reflexive operator r .

Definition (1.14):

Let $A = A^+ \oplus A^-$ be a $\mathbb{Z}/2$ -graded Banach K -algebra with a graded involution

$$\#: A \rightarrow A ; a \mapsto \alpha a, \alpha = \pm 1, \text{ for all } a \in A.$$

The reflexive operator r acting on $C_n(A) = A^{\otimes(n+1)}, n = 0, 1, \dots$, by the graded involution $\#$ is given by

$$r : C_n(A) \rightarrow C_n(A)$$

such that

$$r(a_0 \otimes a_1 \otimes \dots \otimes a_n) = \alpha (-1)^{\lambda(\lambda+1)/2} a_0^\# \otimes a_n^\# \otimes \dots \otimes a_1^\# \dots \tag{1.1}$$

where $\alpha = \pm 1, a_i^\# = im(a_i)$ under the involution $\#$ and $\lambda = |a_0^\#| \sum_{i=1}^n |a_i^\#| = |a_0^\#| (|a_n^\#| + \dots + |a_1^\#|)$. Since

$|a_i^\#| = |\alpha a_i| = \alpha |a_i|, 0 \leq i \leq n$, then

$$\lambda = |a_0| \sum_{i=1}^n |a_i| = |a_0| (|a_n| + \dots + |a_1|) \dots \tag{1.2}$$

Special cases:

(a) When $\alpha = +$, i.e. $a \in A = A^+$, we have $|a_i| = 0$ and $\lambda = 0$, in (1.1) we have

$$r(a_0 \otimes a_1 \dots \otimes a_n) = a_0^\# \otimes a_n^\# \otimes \dots \otimes a_1^\#.$$

(b) When $\alpha = -$, i.e. $a \in A = A^-$, we have $|a_i| = 1$ and $\lambda = |a_0| \sum_{i=1}^n 1 = n$, that is $\lambda(\lambda+1)/2 = n(n+1)/2$, in

(1.1) we have

$$r(a_0 \otimes a_1 \otimes \dots \otimes a_n) = -(-1)^{n(n+1)/2} a_0^\# \otimes a_n^\# \otimes \dots \otimes a_1^\#.$$

For example, $r(a_0 \otimes a_1) = \alpha(-1)^{\lambda(\lambda+1)/2} a_0^\# \otimes a_1^\#$, where $\lambda = |a_0||a_1|$, $\alpha = \pm$.

Lemma (1.15):

The reflexive operator r , defined above satisfies the relation :

$$r^2 = 1,$$

where $1 = id_A : A \rightarrow A$ is the identity map of A .

Proof :

$$\begin{aligned} r^2(a_0 \otimes a_1 \otimes \dots \otimes a_n) &= r(r(a_0 \otimes a_1 \otimes \dots \otimes a_n)) \\ &= \alpha(-1)^{\lambda(\lambda+1)/2} r(a_0^\# \otimes a_n^\# \otimes \dots \otimes a_1^\#) \\ &= \alpha^2(-1)^{\lambda(\lambda+1)} a_0^{\#\#} \otimes a_1^{\#\#} \otimes \dots \otimes a_n^{\#\#}. \end{aligned}$$

Since $a_i^{\#\#} = (a_i^\#)^\# = a_i$ and $\alpha^2 = 1$ as $\alpha = \pm$, and also $(-1)^{\lambda(\lambda+1)} = 1$ as $\lambda(\lambda+1)$ is always even if λ is even or odd.

Thus, we have $r^2(a_0 \otimes a_1 \otimes \dots \otimes a_n) = a_0 \otimes a_1 \otimes \dots \otimes a_n$, i.e. $r^2 = id_A$.

2 Dihedral cohomology of $\mathbb{Z}/2$ -graded Banach algebras.

We use the references [4], [5], and [6]. For the basic concepts and constructions of dihedral homology and cohomology, see [10].

Let $A = A^+ \oplus A^-$ be a $\mathbb{Z}/2$ -graded Banach algebra over K . The topological dual space of A , $A^* = Hom(A, K)$ will be given over the $\mathbb{Z}/2$ -grading by $(A^*)^\alpha = (A^\alpha)^*$, $\alpha = \pm$. The associated involution on A^* is the transpose map of involution on A , that is

$$\#: A \rightarrow A; a \mapsto \alpha a \Rightarrow \#^* : A^* \rightarrow A^*; (a)^* \mapsto (\alpha a)^* = \alpha a^*.$$

Let A be a unital $\mathbb{Z}/2$ -graded Banach algebra over K with a graded involution $\#: A \rightarrow A; a \mapsto \alpha a$, $\alpha = \pm$.

Consider the codihedral $K[\mathbb{Z}/2]$ -module $C(A) = (C^n(A), b^n, t^n, r^n)$,

where $C^n(A) = Hom_K(A^{\otimes n+1}, K)$, $n \geq 0$, is the $\mathbb{Z}/2$ -graded Banach space of $(n+1)$ -graded bounded linear maps (continuous) from A to K . These maps are called cochain maps $f : A^{\otimes n+1} \rightarrow K$, $C^0(A) = Hom_K(A, K) = A^*$, where $b^n : C^n(A) \rightarrow C^{n+1}(A)$, given by:

$$b^n f(a_0 \otimes \dots \otimes a_n) = \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} (-1)^i f(a_0 \otimes \dots \otimes a_i a_{i+1} \otimes \dots \otimes a_n)$$

$$+(-1)^{n+|a_n|(|a_0|+\dots+|a_{n-1}|)} f(a_n a_0 \otimes a_1 \otimes \dots \otimes a_{n-1}) \quad (2.1),$$

cyclic operator $t^n : C^n(A) \rightarrow C^n(A)$, given by

$$t^n f(a_0 \otimes \dots \otimes a_{n-1} \otimes a_n) = (-1)^{|a_n|(|a_0|+\dots+|a_{n-1}|)} f(a_n \otimes a_0 \otimes \dots \otimes a_{n-1}) \quad (2.2),$$

and reflexive operator $r^n : C^n(A) \rightarrow C^n(A)$, given by

$$r^n f(a_0 \otimes a_1 \otimes \dots \otimes a_n) = \alpha(-1)^{\lambda(\lambda+1)/2} f(a_0^\# \otimes a_n^\# \otimes \dots \otimes a_1^\#),$$

where $\alpha = \pm 1$, $a_i^\# = im(a_i)$ under the involution $\#$ and $\lambda = |a_0|(|a_n| + \dots + |a_1|)$.

The complexes $CC^n(A)$, ${}_\alpha CR^n(A)$ and ${}_\alpha CD^n(A)$ are called the cyclic, reflexive and dihedral complexes and their cohomologies give the cyclic reflexive and dihedral cohomology groups: $HC^n(A)$, ${}_\alpha HR^n(A)$ and, ${}_\alpha HD^n(A)$ respectively. the relation between the cyclic and dihedral cohomologies of Banach algebra is given by the following assertion [6].

The following isomorphism holds :

$$HC^n(A) \approx {}_-HD^n(A) \oplus {}_+HD^n(A).$$

Notes :

1- When $\alpha = +$, we have $|a_i| = 0$, then $\varepsilon = |a_n|(|a_0| + \dots + |a_{n-1}|) = 0$, in (2.1), we have

$$b^n f(a_0 \otimes \dots \otimes a_n) = \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} (-1)^i f(a_0 \otimes \dots \otimes a_i a_{i+1} \otimes \dots \otimes a_n) + (-1)^n f(a_n a_0 \otimes a_1 \otimes \dots \otimes a_{n-1})$$

which is a

trivially graded case ($A = A^+$). See [9].

When $\alpha = -$, ($A = A^-$) we have $|a_i| = 1$, then $\varepsilon = |a_n|(|a_0| + \dots + |a_{n-1}|) = n$, and $\varepsilon + n = 2n$. Since $(-1)^{\varepsilon+n} = (-1)^{2n} = 1$ as $2n$ is always even, in (2.1), we have

$$b^n f(a_0 \otimes \dots \otimes a_n) = \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} (-1)^i f(a_0 \otimes \dots \otimes a_i a_{i+1} \otimes \dots \otimes a_n) + f(a_n a_0 \otimes a_1 \otimes \dots \otimes a_{n-1}).$$

2- When $\alpha = +$, ($A = A^+$), we have $|a_i| = 0$, then $\varepsilon = |a_n|(|a_0| + \dots + |a_{n-1}|) = 0$,

in (2.1), we have

$$t^n f(a_0 \otimes \dots \otimes a_{n-1} \otimes a_n) = f(a_n \otimes a_0 \otimes \dots \otimes a_{n-1}).$$

When $\alpha = -$, ($A = A^-$) we have $|a_i| = 1$, then $\varepsilon = |a_n|(|a_0| + \dots + |a_{n-1}|) = n$,

in (2.1), we have

$$t^n f(a_0 \otimes \dots \otimes a_{n-1} \otimes a_n) = (-1)^n f(a_n \otimes a_0 \otimes \dots \otimes a_{n-1}),$$

which is a trivially graded case. See [9].

2.1 Low-Dimensional Computations.

Example (2.1.1)[4]:

$H^0(A, A^*)$ is the space of all bounded graded traces, i.e.

$$H^0(A, A^*) = \{ \text{all } f \in \text{Hom}_K(A, K) \mid f = 0 \text{ on } [A, A]_{gr} \},$$

which is the dual space of $H_0(A, A) = A / [A, A]_{gr}$.

Proof :

Consider the Hochschild complex :

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &\longrightarrow C^0(A, A^*) \xrightarrow{b_1} C^1(A, A^*) \longrightarrow \dots, \text{ i.e.} \\ 0 &\longrightarrow \text{Hom}_K(A, K) \xrightarrow{b_1} \text{Hom}_K(A \otimes A, K) \longrightarrow \dots \end{aligned}$$

$H^0(A, A^*) = \ker(b_1)$, where

$$b_1 f(a_0 \otimes a_1) = f(a_0 a_1) + (-1)^{1+|a_1||a_0|} f(a_1 a_0) = f(a_0 a_1 - (-1)^{|a_1||a_0|} a_1 a_0) = f([a_0, a_1]_{gr}).$$

A cocycle $f \in \text{Hom}_K(A, K) = A^*$ is inside $\ker(b_1)$ if

$$0 = b_1 f(a_0 \otimes a_1) = f([a_0, a_1]),$$

i.e. f vanishes on the subgroup $[A, A]_{gr}$, i.e. $f : A \rightarrow K$ is a bounded graded trace. Then

$$\begin{aligned} H^0(A, A^*) &= \ker(b_1) = \{ \text{all } f \in \text{Hom}_K(A, K) \mid f = 0 \text{ on } [A, A]_{gr} \} \\ &= C^0(A, A^*) = \text{Hom}_K(A, K) \end{aligned}$$

where, $C^q(A, A^*) = \text{Hom}_K(A^{\otimes q}, A^*) = \text{Hom}_K(A^{\otimes(q+1)}, K)$.

Remark :

Since $f : A \rightarrow K$ is a bounded graded trace, then $[A, A]_{gr} = 0$, so, $H_0(A, A) = A$ and $\text{Hom}_K(H_0(A, A), K) = \text{Hom}_K(A, K) = A^* = H^*(A, A^*)$.

More generally, Since K is a field, it is clear that $H^n(A, A^*)$ is the dual space of $H_n(A, A)$. Hence $H^*(A, A^*) = H_*(A, A)^*$.

Lemma (2.1.2) [5]:

For any unital $\mathbb{Z}/2$ -graded Banach algebra A , we show that $H^1(A, A^*) = \text{Der}_{gr}(A, A^*) / \{ \text{Continuous graded inner derivations} \}$, where $\text{Der}_{gr}(A, A^*)$ is the K -module of all continuous graded derivations from $A \otimes A$ to K ($f \in \text{Hom}_K(A \otimes A, K)$).

Proof :

Consider the Hochschild complex :

$$0 \longrightarrow \text{Hom}_K(A, K) \xrightarrow{b_1} \text{Hom}_K(A \otimes A, K) \xrightarrow{b_2} \text{Hom}_K(A \otimes A \otimes A, K) \longrightarrow \dots$$

We know that $H^0(A, A^*) = \frac{\ker(b_2)}{\text{im}(b_1)}$, and $b_1 f(a_0 \otimes a_1) = f([a_0, a_1]_{gr})$.

The coboundaries in degree 1 are maps $f : A \otimes A \rightarrow K$, defined by $f(a_0 \otimes a_1) \mapsto f([a_0, a_1]_{gr})$ or

$$a_0 \otimes a_1 \mapsto [a_0, a_1]_{gr} = a_0 a_1 - (-1)^{|a_1||a_0|} a_1 a_0 \in K.$$

These functions are continuous graded K -derivations which are called continuous graded inner derivations.

Then:

$$im(b_1) = \{ \text{all } f : A \otimes A \rightarrow K : a_0 \otimes a_1 \mapsto [a_0, a_1]_{gr} \} =$$

$$\{ \text{Continuous graded inner derivations} \}.$$

$b_2 f(a_0 \otimes a_1 \otimes a_2) = f(a_0 a_1 \otimes a_2) - f(a_0 \otimes a_1 a_2) + (-1)^{|a_2|(|a_0|+|a_1|)} f(a_2 a_0 \otimes a_1)$, since f is a cocycle in degree 1, then $b_2 f(a_0 \otimes a_1 \otimes a_2) = 0$, i.e.

$$f(a_0 \otimes a_1 a_2) = f(a_0 a_1 \otimes a_2) + (-1)^{|a_2|(|a_0|+|a_1|)} f(a_2 a_0 \otimes a_1) \quad (2.3).$$

Hence, $f : A \otimes A \rightarrow K$ is a continuous graded derivation. Thus we have

$$\ker(b_2) = \{ \text{all } f \in Hom_K(A \otimes A, K) : f \text{ is a continuous graded derivation} \}$$

$$= Der_{gr}(A \otimes A, K) = Der_{gr}(A, A^*), \text{ as}$$

$$Der_{gr}(A, A^*) = Der_{gr}(A, Hom_K(A, K)) = Der_{gr}(A \otimes A, K),$$

thus we get

$$H^1(A, A^*) = Der_{gr}(A, A^*) / \{ \text{Continuous graded inner derivations} \}.$$

Note that all bounded linear maps, or operators are continuous.

Remark [2]:

A $\mathbb{Z}/2$ -graded Banach algebra A is weakly amenable if $H^1(A, A^*) = \{0\}$.

For any unital $\mathbb{Z}/2$ -graded Banach algebra A over K .

We expect that : $HR^0(A) \cong HC^0(A) \cong HD^0(A) \cong H^0(A, A^*)$, the space of all bounded graded traces, i.e.

$$H^0(A, A^*) = \{ \text{all } f \in Hom_K(A, K) \mid f = 0 \text{ on } [A, A]_{gr} \}, \text{ which is the dual space of}$$

$$H_0(A, A) = A / [A, A]_{gr}.$$

References

- [1] Arveson, W., An invitation to C*-algebras, Springer-Verlag, New York-Heidelberg, 1976.
- [2] Christensen, E. and Sinclair, A.M., On the vanishing of $H^n(A, M^*)$ for certain $\mathbb{C}^*$ -algebra, Pacific J. Math., 137 (1989), 55-63.
- [3] Dales, H.G., Banach algebras and automatic continuity, Clarendon Press, Oxford, 2000.
- [4] Gouda, Y.Gh., On the cyclic and dihedral cohomology of Banach spaces, Publ. Math. Debrecen 51/ 1-2 (1997), 67-80.
- [5] Gouda, Y.Gh., The relative dihedral homology of involutive algebras, Internat. J. Math. & Math. Sci. Vol.2, N0.4(1999) 807-815.

- [6] Gouda, Y.Gh., On the dihedral cohomology of operator algebra, Int. J. of algebra. Vol.4, No. 23(2010),1134-1144.
- [7] Johnson, B., Introduction to cohomology in Banach algebras. In: Algebras in Analysis. London, New York: Academic Press 1975
- [8] Kassel, C., A Künneth formula for the cyclic cohomology of $\mathbb{Z}/2$ -graded algebras, Math. Ann.,257 (1986), 683-699.
- [9] Kassel, C., Homology and cohomology of associative algebras, -A concise introduction to cyclic homology- Advanced School on Non-commutative Geometry ICTP, Trieste, August 2004.
- [10] Krasauskas, R.L., Lapin, S.V. and Solov'ev, Yu. P., Dihedral homology and cohomology. Basic concepts and constructions, Mat. Sb. (N.S.) 133 (175) (1987), no. 1, 25–48, (Russian).
- [11] Megginson, R., An introduction to Banach space theory, (Springer-Verlag, New York, 1998).